

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF NOVEL HERBAL FORMULATION FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF PSORIASIS

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ABSTRACT

Psoriasis is a chronic autoimmune condition affecting millions worldwide, including a significant population in India. Psoriasis is a chronic skin condition characterized by the rapid buildup of skin cells, forming thick, silvery scales and itchy, dry, and red patches. This study aims to assess this innovative formulation's effectiveness and safety in managing psoriasis. This study presents the development and evaluation of a novel herbal formulation for psoriasis management utilizing the solvent evaporation method to produce microspheres. Based on the result, batch F-2 showed promising results. The Phytochemical screening of the drug revealed the presence of several phytoconstituents. Alkaloids, glycosides, carbohydrates, flavonoids, and saponins are all found in alcoholic solutions of extracts. The obtained particle size was 202.8 micrometers, the percent yield was 58.82% and %Entrapment efficiency was 80.61%. The physicochemical compatibility between Psoralen and other excipients was confirmed by using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The absorption maxima of psoralen were measured by a UV-visible spectrophotometer and found to be 247 nm. In conclusion, we conclude that multiple advantages are achieved by incorporating Pure Psoralen into microspheres, including enhanced stability, prolonged drug release, and improved skin permeability. These properties enable targeted and sustained delivery of Psoralen, optimizing therapeutic efficacy while minimizing potential side effects. This study aims to assess this innovative formulation's effectiveness and safety in managing psoriasis.

KEYWORDS: Psoriasis, Evaluation, Entrapment Efficiency, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, Microspheres.

INTRODUCTION

According to the survey, 125 million of the total population is suffering from psoriasis worldwide. According to global psoriasis atlas data, an estimated 3.59 million people in India are affected. Psoriasis is a chronic skin condition characterized by the rapid buildup of skin cells, forming thick, silvery scales and itchy, dry, and red patches. Various conventional dosage forms are available but have some drawbacks like low bioavailability, increased dosing frequency, etc. So, we formulated and evaluated the Psoralen-loaded Microsphere Gel for the management of Psoriasis. Microspheres enhance the environmental stability of the drug and in addition to that it is lipophilic which enhances permeability through the skin. By incorporating Pure Psoralen into microspheres, several advantages can be achieved. Firstly, microspheres can protect the bioactive components of Psoralen from degradation, ensuring their stability and enhancing their shelf life. Secondly, the controlled release properties of microspheres can provide sustained and targeted delivery of Psoralen, optimizing its therapeutic effects in a dose-dependent manner and minimizing potential side effects including nausea, vomiting, erythema, pruritus, xerosis, skin pain due to phototoxic damage of dermal nerve at a higher dose at once. Additionally, the incorporation of microspheres into a gel matrix offers the advantage of easy application, providing a convenient and user-friendly formulation.[1]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Material:

The dried seeds of *Psoralea corylifolia* were collected from YUCCA ENTERPRISES at A-246, Antop Hill Warehousing Co., Barkat Ali Naka, VIT Marg, WADALI(E), MUMBAI 400 037, INDIA.

Authentication of Plant Material:

Dried plant material would be authenticated by macroscopical and microscopical evaluation compared with the reference standard book (Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants – Vol 3).

Extraction and Isolation of Psoralen: [2]**Preliminary Phytochemical Screening:[3][4][5]**

The extract obtained from successive solvent extraction was then subjected to various qualitative chemical tests to determine the presence of different phytoconstituents like alkaloids, glycosides, carbohydrates, phenolics and tannins, phytosterols, fixed oils and fats, proteins and amino acids, flavonoids, saponins, gums, and mucilage using reported methods.

Physicochemical evaluation of drug: [3][4][5][6][7][8][9]

Physicochemical parameters like Foreign organic matter, Determination of moisture content, Ash values e.g.(a) Total ash (b) Acid insoluble ash (c) Water soluble ash; Extractive values e.g. (a) Hot percolation (b) Cold Maceration such

as Ethanol soluble extractive, Water-soluble extractive, Ether soluble extractive; Foaming index; Determination of swelling index were checked.

TLC Identity Test:[10]

Mobile phase: Toluene: Ethyl acetate (7.0:3.0)

Take isolated psoralen dissolved in methanol (test solution) and marketed psoralen dissolved in methanol (standard solution). Put both spots on a silica gel plate and this plate was put into the mobile phase.

Visualization: Visualize the plate under the UV region at 254nm and note the R_f values.[10]

Absorption Maxima:[11] Drug molecules in solution when exposed to light in the visible/ultraviolet region of the spectrum absorb light of a particular wavelength depending on the type of electronic transition associated with the absorption. The drug solution (4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was taken in the cuvette scanned in the range of 230 to 400 nm in a UV spectrophotometer. [11]

Calibration Curve of Psoralen

Preparation of phosphate buffer pH 6.8[12]

Phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was prepared using the following methods (I.P.1996). Disodium hydrogen phosphate (6.8g) was dissolved in 500ml of distilled water and sodium hydroxide (1g) was dissolved in distilled water from that 224ml of the solution was taken and added with the above solution and the volume was made up to 1 liter with distilled water. The pH was adjusted to 6.8 before quantitative estimation.[12]

Preparation of Calibration Curve of Psoralen in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8[12]

An accurately weighed quantity (100mg) of Psoralen was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask was dissolved in a small amount of buffer pH 6.8, and the volume was made up with the same buffer to make the standard stock solution of 1mg/ml. From the stock 1ml was taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up the volume with the buffer, from this solution 0.5ml to 3ml solution was transferred to a 10 ml volumetric flask and made up the required volume with buffer, and the resulting concentration ranging from 5 to 30 micrograms per ml. The absorbance of these solutions was determined at 247 nm using a UV spectrophotometer. The standard curve was constructed between the absorbance and concentration. This standard curve was linearly regressed and statistical parameters related to it were derived.[12]

Method for Preparation of Microspheres:[13]

In one beaker, take 800 mg Ethyl cellulose + 10 ml Chloroform and mix them for 5 minutes with the help of a magnetic stirrer.

After that, 50 mg of Psoralen was added to the above mixture and mixed again for 5 minutes. The mixture of polymer and drug is then sonicated using a bath sonicator for 7 minutes.

In another beaker, add 100 mg of Polyvinyl alcohol in 50 ml of distilled water. This mixture was continuously stirred by using the homogenizer.

Filter it with Whatman filter paper and leave the microspheres to dry properly.

Evaluation of Microspheres:

Micromeritic properties:[14] Microspheres were characterized for their micromeritic properties such as particle size, shape, bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, Hausner's ratio, and angle of repose.

Particle Size:[14] Microspheres are characterized by their diameter, and this is a crucial parameter as it affects their behavior in formulations and applications. Microspheres are placed on the microscope slide, and the microscope is focused to obtain a clear image. The ocular micrometer is then used to measure the diameter of individual microspheres.

Shape:[14] Microspheres are generally expected to have a spherical shape, as the name suggests. However, variations in shape can occur, and uniformity in shape is important for consistent performance.

Bulk Density:[14] The bulk density of microspheres is an important parameter that influences their flow properties, handling, and packaging. It is the mass of the microspheres divided by their bulk volume occupied by the microspheres was noted without disturbing the cylinder and bulk density was calculated using the following equation;

$$\text{Bulk density (Pb)} = M / V$$

Tapped Density:[15] The maximum packing density of a powder under tapping or vibration. It is achieved by tapping a container containing the powder until little volume change occurs. The tapped density of microspheres is significant for applications where packing efficiency is crucial. This property is especially relevant in drug formulation where achieving a consistent dose is essential. The tapping method was used to determine the tapped density. The cylinder containing a known amount (M) of microspheres was subjected to a fixed number of taps (approximately 100) until the bed of microspheres had reached the minimum. The final volume after tapping 'Vo' was recorded and the tap density was calculated by the following equation:

$$\text{Tapped density (Pp)} = M / (Vo)$$

Compressibility/Carr's Index:[15] The compressibility index of microspheres gives insight into their ability to decrease in volume under pressure. This property is crucial in processes where compression or compaction is involved.

Calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Carr's index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Bulk density} - \text{Tapped density}}{\text{Tapped density}} \times 100$$

Hausner's Ratio:[15] A ratio of the tapped density to the bulk density. Hausner's ratio provides information on the flowability of microspheres. A lower Hausner's ratio indicates better flow properties, which is important in pharmaceutical manufacturing for uniform filling of capsules or tablets.

$$\text{Hausner's Ratio} = \text{Tapped Density} / \text{Bulk Density}$$

Angle of Repose:[14] The maximum angle at which a pile of powder remains stable without sliding. It is measured by allowing the powder to flow freely and form a cone, and then measuring the angle of the cone. The angle of repose is relevant for understanding the ability of microspheres to create a stable pile without sliding. This property is essential in processes involving the free flow of microspheres, such as in hoppers or during transportation. The angle of repose of the microspheres, which is the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of microspheres and the horizontal plane, was obtained by the fixed funnel method using the formula;

angle of Repose, $\tan \theta = h/r$ where, h = height of heap, r =radius of heap

Percent yield:[16][17] The percentage yield of the prepared microsphere was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ yield} = (\text{Weight of dried microspheres}) / (\text{Amount of Drug} + \text{Amount of polymer})$$

Entrapment efficiency:[18] An accurately weighed quantity of microspheres was crushed into powder and added to 100 ml of distilled water. The mixture was kept for 92 hours. Then the solution was filtered and drug content was estimated by UV spectrophotometer at 262 nm. The drug entrapment efficiency was determined by using the formula,

$$\% \text{ Entrapment Efficiency} = (\text{experimental drug content}/\text{theoretical drug content}) \times 100$$

FTIR:[19] Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were obtained by using Shimadzu FTIR- 8400 Spectrophotometer. The samples were previously ground and mixed thoroughly with potassium bromide, an infrared transparent matrix, at a 1:5 (Sample/KBr) ratio, respectively. The KBr discs were prepared by compressing the powders at a pressure of 5 tons for 5 min in a hydraulic press.

Method for Preparation of Gel: [20]

Take 1 gm of Gelatin in 50 ml of distilled water and stir continuously in unidirectional motion to get proper mixing.

After proper mixing, add prepared microspheres to that gel base, stir it for 5 minutes for consistency, and add 0.5 gm of Methylparaben as a preservative.

After getting the required consistency, Gel was incorporated with microspheres and it was formed.

Evaluation of Gel:

Physical Parameters (Color and Appearance):[21] Visual inspection is performed to assess the color and appearance of the gel.

pH Measurement:[21] About 1 g of the gel is accurately weighed and dispersed in 100 ml of purified water. The pH of the resulting dispersion is measured using a digital pH meter. The pH measurements are conducted in triplicate, and the average values are calculated.

Drug Content Determination:[22] About 1 g of the gel is weighed and dissolved in 100 ml of 6.8 phosphate buffer. Appropriate dilutions are made with buffer, and the solution is filtered. The absorbance of the filtered solution is measured spectrophotometrically at 427 nm.

Spreadability:[22] About 0.5 g of gel is placed in a circle with a 1 cm diameter on a 20×20 cm glass plate. A second glass plate is placed over it, and a weight of 500 g is allowed to rest on the upper glass plate for 5 minutes. The increase in the diameter of the gel due to spreading is noted.

Viscosity:[21] The viscosity of the prepared gel is measured using a DV-E Brookfield viscometer. The gels are rotated at 30 rpm using spindle no. 64, and the corresponding dial reading is noted.

Diffusivity study:[23][24] In-vitro studies greatly aid the design and development of the transdermal drug delivery system. The diffusion studies were done to get an idea of the permeation of the drug through the barrier from the transdermal system. Usually, two types of diffusion cells are used horizontal and vertical. The Franz and Keshary Chien (K-C) type of diffusion cells are horizontal type of cells. In this work, a K-C type of diffusion cell was used. Diffusion cells generally comprise two compartments, one containing the active compartment (donor compartment) and the other containing receptor solution (receptor compartment), separated by a barrier i.e. rat's skin. The cell consisted of a sampling port and temperature-maintaining jacket. The outlet and inlet were connected with a latex tube so the jacket had stagnant water inside and the heat was provided by the hot plate. The star head magnet was used to stir the receptor solution using a magnetic stirrer. The rat's skin was placed on the receptor compartment and both compartments were held tight by clamps. The glass diffusion cell (Keshary–Chien type) was used for release studies. The rat's skin membrane was mounted between the donor and receptor compartment, such that the epidermal surface faced the donor compartment. The microsphere is fixed between donor and receptor compartments clamped together and placed in a water bath maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The volume of the receptor cell was 22 ml and the effective surface area available for permeation was 4.9062 cm². The receptor compartment is filled with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. The hydrodynamics of the receptor fluid were maintained by stirring the fluid at 600 rpm with a star head magnet. Samples of 2 ml were withdrawn at specific intervals of time. The same volume of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was added to the receptor compartment to maintain sink conditions and the samples were analyzed at 238 nm UV-Spectro-photometrically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemical screening

The extracts were undergoing phytochemical screening which revealed the presence of various phytoconstituents. Results show different classes of phytoconstituents in each extract. The results are shown in the below table:

Table 1 Results of phytochemical screening

Chemical constituent	Chemical test	Alcoholic Extracts	Aqueous Extracts
Alkaloids	Mayer's test	+	-
Carbohydrates	Molisch's test	+	+
Glycosides	Balget Test	+	+
Flavonoids	Lead acetate test	+	+
Saponins	Froth's test	+	+
Steroids	Liebermann Burchard's Test	-	-
Phenolics/tannins	Ferric chloride test	-	-

(+ve: Sign indicates Positive Result, -ve: Sign indicates Negative Result)

This study concluded that alkaloids, carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, and saponins are present in the alcoholic extract of *Psoralea corylifolia* whereas, steroids and tannins were absent. While, in the aqueous extract of *Psoralea corylifolia* carbohydrates, glycosides, flavonoids, and saponins are present and alkaloids, steroids, and tannins are absent.

Physicochemical evaluation of drug

Table 2 Results of Physicochemical evaluation of drug

Sr. no.	Physical parameters	Result	STD range as per IP
1	Foreign organic matter	0.78%	Not more than 2 %
2	Moisture content	5%	-
3	Total ash	7.2%	Not more than 9%
4	Acid insoluble ash	3.22%	Not more than 0.8 %
5	Water soluble ash	3.5%	-
6	Foaming Index	<100	-

DRUG IDENTIFICATION

Thin Layer Chromatography

Fig.1 TLC of Psoralen

The standard R_f value of Psoralen is 0.47.

Therefore, it is concluded that the spots of isolated psoralen and marketed psoralen that have R_f values equal to 0.43 and 0.44 are Psoralen.

Absorption Maxima

It exhibits maxima at 247nm. Therefore, all the further measurements were taken at 247 nm.

Fig.2 Absorption maxima of Psoralen

Table 3 Absorbance maxima of Psoralen

Sr.no.	Wavelength	Absorbance
1	247.00	0.4009

The characteristics peak of the drug was obtained at 247 nm.

Preparation of Calibration Curve of Psoralen in Phosphate buffer pH 6.8

The standard curve was constructed between the absorbance and concentration. This standard curve was linearly regressed and statistical parameters related to it were derived.

Table 4 Calibration curve of Psoralen

Sr.no.	Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 247 nm
1	2	0.264
2	4	0.391

3	6	0.511
4	8	0.658
5	10	0.766

$$r^2 = 0.9995$$

Fig.3 Calibration curve of Psoralen

Development of Herbal Formulation

Table 5 Development of Formulation

Formulation	Drug	Dosage	%Entrapment Efficiency
Formulation-1 (F-1)	Ethyl cellulose Chloroform Psoralen Poly Vinyl Alcohol (PVA) Water	400 mg 10 ml 50 mg [25] 100 mg 50 ml	72.91%
Formulation-2 (F-2)	Ethyl cellulose Chloroform Psoralen Poly Vinyl Alcohol (PVA) Water	800 mg 10 ml 50 mg [25] 100 mg 50 ml	80.61%

F-1 and F-2 batches were using Polymer (Ethyl cellulose 400mg and 800 mg) and Polyvinyl alcohol (100 mg). So observed %EE is shown in the above table. Maximum %EE is observed in the F-2 batch with Ethyl cellulose 800 mg (0.8 g) and polyvinyl alcohol 100 mg. So, Ethyl cellulose 800 mg is selected for the preparation of Microspheres.

Evaluation parameters of the prepared microspheres

Table 6 Result of Evaluation parameters of prepared microspheres

Sr. no.	Evaluation Parameters	Result	Inference
1	Particle size	202.8 μm	-
2	Shape	Spherical	-
3	Bulk density (g/cm^3)	$0.43 \pm 0.15 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$	-
4	Tapped density (g/cm^3)	$0.47 \pm 0.2 \text{ g}/\text{cm}^3$	-
5	Compressibility index/Carr's index (%)	11.5%	Good
6	Hausner's ratio (HR)	1.09	Excellent
7	Angle of repose (θ)	28 ± 0.42	Excellent
8	Percent yield (% yield)	58.52%	-
9	% Entrapment efficiency	80.61%	-

FTIR (Fourier-transform infrared)

Fig.5 FTIR of Psoralen

Table 7 Interpretation of FTIR of Psoralen

Sr. no.	Functional Group	Types of Vibration	STD Wave number (cm-1)	Wave number (cm-1)
1	C-O	Stretching	1180 – 1200	1185.74
2	C=C	Stretching	1500 – 1600	1576.47
3	C-H	Stretching	2927 – 3100	3159.72
4	C=O	Stretching	1700 – 1750	1700.53

Fig.6 FTIR of Psoralen + Ethyl cellulose

Table 8 Interpretation of FTIR of Psoralen + Ethyl cellulose

Sr. no.	Functional Group	Types of Vibration	STD Wave number(cm-1)	Wave number (cm-1)
1	C=O	Stretching	1700-1750	1751.52
2	C-H	Stretching	2700-2900	2867.38
3	C=C	Stretching	1500-1600	1576.47
4	C-H	Stretching	2927-3100	2974.33
5	C=O	Stretching	1700-1750	1700.53
6	C-H	Stretching	1320-1440	1437.08
7	C-O	Stretching	1180-1200	1055.97
8	C-H	Bending	1320-1440	1373.98

Fig.7 FTIR of Psoralen-loaded Microspheres

Table 9 Interpretation of FTIR of Psoralen-loaded Microspheres

Sr. no.	Functional Group	Types of Vibration	STD Wave number(cm-1)	Wave number (cm-1)
1	C-O	Stretching	1180-1200	1284.49
2	C=C	Stretching	1500-1600	1576.47

FTIR of the sample spectrum showed all the characteristic peaks of functional groups present in the sample. The observed frequency of the sample was found within the standard range of the functional group and thus it identifies the sample.

Morphological Study of Microspheres

Prepared Microspheres were characterized by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

8(a)

8(b)

Fig.8 (a) and (b) SEM Photography of Microspheres

Evaluation parameters of the prepared gel

Prepared Microspheres were incorporated into a 1% Gelatin Gel base to form a gel, and the following parameters

Table 10 Result of evaluation parameters of prepared gel

Evaluation parameters	Result
Color	Colorless
pH	6.7
Viscosity (Cps)	38500 Cps
Drug content (%)	92.83%
Spreadability (cm)	5.6 cm

Diffusivity Study:

Fig.9 Franz Diffusion cell

The comparison for the Ex vivo Diffusion study of Psoralen Microspheres gel and control gel was carried out. Comparison of Cumulative drug release (%) of Microspheres gel and control gel in table-11 and figure-10.

Table 11 Ex-vivo Diffusion study

Sr.no.	Time (hour)	Cumulative Percentage Drug Release of Psoralen Microspheres gel (%)	Psoralen Control gel (%)
1	0	0	0
2	0.5	9.51	9.51
3	1	13.15	13.15
4	2	17.56	15.06
5	3	22.11	18.46
6	4	27.53	20.99
7	5	31.34	22.72
8	6	37.36	23.9
9	7	44.22	24.71
10	8	46.47	25.51

Fig.10 Diffusion Profile

There was a comparison of the % Drug diffusion of Microspheres gel and control gel. This comparison indicates that microspheres gel improves ex vivo permeation as compared to the control gel.

CONCLUSION

The conclusions drawn from the present investigation are given below:

The preformulation studies such as thin layer chromatography, Absorbance maxima, FT- IR spectrum of the drug, and sample were found within range. The Psoralen sample was authenticated by the FT-IR spectrum. The wavelength of Psoralen was found to be 247 nm. The assay of Psoralen suggested that it was pure.

Microspheres were prepared with the Solvent evaporation method. From the result of preliminary trials, Ethyl cellulose was selected as polymer, and polyvinyl alcohol, and chloroform were used as organic solvents and water as an aqueous phase.

Optimized Psoralen microspheres were evaluated, and particle size was found to be 202.8 μm and, the %EE was 80.61%. Psoralen Microspheres were then incorporated into the gel and further evaluated for viscosity, pH, % drug content, and ex-vivo diffusion study. It was also compared with the control gel for ex-vivo studies, which showed that the Psoralen microspheres gel was better than the control gel.

Multiple advantages are achieved by incorporating Pure Psoralen into microspheres, including enhanced stability, prolonged drug release, and improved skin permeability. These properties enable targeted and sustained delivery of Psoralen, optimizing therapeutic efficacy while minimizing potential side effects.

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